

**PREVALANCE EFFECT OF CHILD ABUSE ON CHILD'S
HEALTH: A PERCEPTION STUDY OF ABAKPA
COMMUNITY ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.**

BY

NNADI, HELEN CHINEDU (PhD),
Department of Sociology and Anthropology
University of Nigeria Nsukka, Nigeria.
Email: helen.nnadi@unn.edu.ng

&

UDECHI, SANDRA CHIZOBA
Department of Sociology and Anthropology,
University of Nigeria Nsukka, Nigeria.

Abstract

Child abuse is a global problem with serious life-long consequences, especially when it affects the health of the child. Such abuse includes abuse of a child by a man, woman or child (bullying) by the use of fear or compulsion to engage children in any illegal activity which does not relate with the moral values of the society like child trafficking, child prostitution, child pornography, and many other similar acts, done against the will of the child. The study examines the prevalence effect of child abuse on child's health in Abakpa community, Enugu State Nigeria. Social Learning theory was adopted as the theoretical framework for the study. Cross sectional survey research design was used for this study. Questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection while In-depth interview was used as complementary data. Multi stage sampling techniques was used to draw data from 200 respondents from nine streets in the community. The data gotten from the field was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Chi-square was used in testing hypotheses. Results revealed that majority of the respondents 94% have been abused, 60.5% have experienced the effect of abuse on their health, most notable effect of the abuse includes; low esteem, depression, anxiety, bruises etc. Majority of the respondents, 71.5% opined that family educational level determines level of child abuse. The study recommends education, increased awareness creation on the various consequences of child abuse and the need for reforming child support services in Abakpa community Enugu State, Nigeria.

Keyword- Abakpa Community, Child Abuse, Health, Prevalence, Enugu LGA, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Child abuse is a social phenomenon that exists in every society, such abuse includes abuse of a child by a man, woman or child (bullying) by the use of fear, compulsion or force to engage children in any illegal activity, other activity which does not relate with the moral values of the society like child trafficking, child prostitution, child pornography, and many other similar acts, which are done against the will of the child in it. Olubukola et al., (2018) opined that child abuse and neglect are prevalent in Nigeria, Abakpa community inclusive. For Fayaz, (2019) “Child maltreatment always occurs when any of these areas of a child's emotional and social growth are neglected or not given adequate attention” pages 871-884. At this age, they have limited knowledge about the natural processes of puberty, sexual health, pregnancy or reproduction UNICEF (2024). The effect of child abuse globally is difficult to determine precisely due to underreporting the cases of child abuse by the victims. However, according to UNICEF (2024) “Nearly 400 million young children worldwide regularly experience violent discipline at home.” This includes physical, sexual, emotional, and neglectful abuse.

In Abakpa community, Enugu state, child abuse had led to serious social problems that have affected families which have cause children to drop out of school both from primary and secondary school. Some parents send their children out to the streets to go and hawk things around or even get them menial jobs like working as house keeper or sales person and they become the bread winner of the family at a tender age when the child is suppose to be in school studying. Street hawking is one of the most important labour challenges that have attracted global attention (World Health Organization (2020). Numerous studies have showed the correlation between poverty and low socioeconomic status on child abuse (Coley et al., 2018; Lund et al., 2017; Torsheim et, al 2018). In a recent report from the Health Behaviour in School-aged Children (HBSC), Torsheim et, al (2018) showed that adolescents from low-affluence families had poorer health, lower life satisfaction, higher levels of obesity and sedentary behaviors, weaker communication with their parents, less social interaction via social media, and lower levels of support from friends and family. Thus making them very vulnerable to child abuse and also reduce the chances of the abuse being reported when it happens (Coley et al., 2018). Socioeconomic factors exert a profound influence on child abuse in Nigeria. In a country where poverty rates remain high and economic opportunities are limited, families often struggle to meet their basic needs, leading to increased stress and tension within households. As a result, parents facing economic hardship may be more prone to resorting to abusive behaviors as a means of exerting control or venting frustration (Bamiwuye et al., 2017). Children from disadvantaged backgrounds are particularly susceptible to exploitation and mistreatment, as they often lack the protection and advocacy necessary to safeguard their rights (Brown

2020). In general, people with disabilities experience domestic and sexual violence at higher rates than people who do not have a form of disability. Neglect in the provision of vital things required by children, be it physical, emotional, and educational is harmful to children as they affect what they needed physiologically and psychologically Adekola, et,al (2022). Child's Right Act clearly stipulates the rights of a child. This act has been adopted by the Federal Republic of Nigeria in 2003, but it is surprising that in Abakpa community there are cases of child abuse. Sexual abuse like rape, attempted rape or sexual assault, inappropriate touch anywhere, inappropriate looking, sexual teasing or innuendo or sexual harassment exposes children to bad health conditions like infection and it also affects them psychologically Bulik & Prescott (2021). Understanding the prevalent effect of child abuse on child's health is crucial for developing effective prevention and intervention policies in Abakpa community of Enugu state, Nigeria. The neighborhood association of Abakpa community in 2023 made an unwritten law that no child under school age should be seen in the street hawking or getting involved in any other activities rather than being in school and this is in order to curtail some of these abuse but still the problem has not been solved, therefore the aim of this study is to investigate the perception of the community on effect of child abuse on child's health in Abakpa community and proffer possible solutions to address this social problem.

Statement of problem

Child abuse is a problem, yet nobody seems to care that much in Nigeria. This is likely due to efforts being directed at solving the more widespread problems of childhood, such as hunger and illness (Adekola et al., 2022). Certain traditional approaches to parenting have poor outcomes for some children, such as the intentional abandoning of severely disabled children or their twins or triplets in some rural communities (Gbenga-Epebinu, Okafor & Olofinbiyi 2020). Education of the masses on the dangers of this menace is needed, and measures to alleviate poverty among the populace need to be radically pursued.. Obuzor & Gabriel-Job(2022). The situation in terms of child abuse is not different in Abakpa community. Indeed there is constant abuse, neglect, deprivation of child's right, physical and sexual abuse in slums areas of Abakpa community. Brown (2020) noted that parental stress can significantly contribute to child abuse, creating a challenging environment for both parents and children. High levels of stress may compromise a parent's ability to cope effectively, leading to frustration, anger, and decreased impulse control. This emotional strain can manifest in harmful behaviors towards the child. Parental stress has been identified as a significant factor contributing to child abuse in Nigeria. The high prevalence of poverty and unemployment in Nigeria places immense pressure on parents to provide for their families, leading to heightened stress levels (Okechukwu & Nwafor, 2019). Also,

for them additionally, factors such as marital conflicts, substance abuse, and limited access to social support further compound parental stress and increase the risk of child abuse.

One long-term study found that up to 80% of abused people had at least one psychiatric disorder at age 21, with problems including depression, anxiety, eating disorders, and suicide attempts (Nelson et al., 2022). In addition to possible immediate adverse physical effects, household dysfunction and childhood maltreatment are strongly associated with many chronic physical and psychological effects, including subsequent ill-health in childhood, adolescence and adulthood, with higher rates of chronic conditions, high-risk health behaviors and shortened lifespan (Zickler 2022). Children who have a history of neglect or physical abuse are at risk of developing psychiatric problems, or a disorganized attachment style. In addition, children who experience child abuse or neglect are 59% more likely to be arrested as juveniles, 28% more likely to be arrested as adults, and 30% more likely to commit violent crime (Fergusson & Mullen 2019). Ineffectual prosecution of offenders in reported cases also contributes to non-disclosure of abuse Yahaya et al, (2016). Against this background that the study tend to explore the prevalent effect of child abuse on child's health in Abakpa community Enugu state, Nigeria and proffer possible policies to reduce the negative effect of child abuse on child's health.

Objectives of Study

The study aimed to determine whether:

1. Individuals with lower educational qualification experiences child abuse more than those with higher educational qualification in Abakpa community.
2. There are significant relationships between most prevalent forms of child abuse and effect on children's health in Abakpa community.
3. There are significant relationships between notable implications of child abuse in Abakpa community and the ratings of their health experiences.

Literature review

Child abuse is a complex phenomenon with multiple causes and effects especially on the health of children. No single factor can be identified as reasons adults behave abusively or neglectfully toward children. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Society for Prevention of Child Abuse and Neglect (ISPCAN) identify multiple factors at the level of the individual, their relationships, their local community, and their society at large, that contribute to influence the occurrence of child maltreatments irrespective of the effects.

Health Implications of Child Abuse

Child abuse often has severe short- and long-term physical, sexual and mental health consequences. These include injuries, including head injuries and severe disability, in particular in young children; post-traumatic stress, anxiety, depression, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) including HIV. Adolescent girls may face additional health issues, including gynecological disorders and unwanted pregnancy. Child maltreatment can affect cognitive and academic performance and is strongly associated with alcohol and drug abuse and smoking – key risk factors for non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as cardiovascular diseases and cancer (World Health Organization, 2022). Child abuse can lead to injuries, impaired growth, and long-term health problems. The immediate health effects of abuse or neglect can be relatively minor (bruises or cuts) or severe (broken bones, hemorrhage, death). Certain injuries, such as rib fractures or femoral fractures in infants that are not yet walking, may increase suspicion of child physical abuse, although such injuries are only seen in a fraction of children suffering physical abuse. Children who have a history of neglect or physical abuse are at risk of developing psychiatric problems, or a disorganized attachment style. In addition, children who experience child abuse or neglect are 59% more likely to be arrested as juveniles, 28% more likely to be arrested as adults, and 30% more likely to commit violent crime (Fergusson & Mullen 2019). Cigarette burns or scald injuries may also prompt evaluation for child physical abuse (Flaherty et al., 2016). Damage results from intracranial hypertension (increased pressure in the skull) after bleeding in the brain, damage to the spinal cord and neck, and rib or bone fractures (Walsh, & DiLillo 2021).

Sexual Health Implications

Child abuse has been noted to correlate to youth pregnancy, with both immediate and long-term sexual consequences. However, research also shows that experiencing sexual violence in early adolescence is linked to subsequent pregnancy (not related to the abusive circumstance) later in adolescence (Zickler 2022).

Behavioural Health Implications: Abused children have been noted to exhibit various types of psychopathology and behavioral deviancy. Diaz et al. (2020), noted that children who experience any form of maltreatment or are more likely to engage in smoking, drinking, and/or drug use when they grow up. This misuse increases their risk of overdose, substance dependency, health problems, and engaging in abusive behaviors in their own families later in life.

Mental Health Implications: Physical and emotional abuse have comparable effects on a child's emotional state and have been linked to childhood depression, low self-compassion, and negative automatic thoughts. Some research suggests that

high stress levels from child abuse may cause structural and functional changes within the brain, and therefore cause emotional and social disruptions (Zhang 2022). Children may block out traumatic memories. Sometimes, this can lead to memory issues and other problems that affect areas of life beyond the abuse. Zhang, (2022), noted that shame and guilt often also result, with children sometimes blaming themselves for the situation or viewing themselves as somehow defective. Thus, they may feel guilty for failing to report a situation of abuse In order to hide the abuse from others; they may withdraw, isolate, and have a hard time making friends.

Emotional or Psychological Abuse: These Involves behaviors that harm a child's self-worth or emotional well-being, including constant criticism, rejection, or isolation. It involves using of words and actions to manipulate or control a child. Emotional abuse behavior is difficult to recognize or document but is often present in all categories of child abuse, including physical and sexual abuse (Plummer 2018). He further noted that the victims of emotional abuse may react by distancing themselves from the abuser, internalizing the abusive words, or fighting back by insulting the abuser. Emotional abuse can result in abnormal or disrupted attachment development, a tendency for victims to blame themselves (self-blame) for the abuse, learned helplessness, and overly passive behavior in order to avoid such a situation again (Singh & Dalh 2021)

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the social learning theory. The theory was proposed by Albert Bandura in 1965. According to Social Learning Theory (SLT), individuals learn behaviors through observation, imitation, and reinforcement from their social environment, including family, peers, and media. In Abakpa, Enugu State, the family unit serves as the primary environment where children observe and internalize behaviors. If children witness positive behaviors from their caregivers, they are likely to model and replicate these behaviors in their own relationships and interactions. For instance, if a child observes their parents using physical or psychological violence as a means of discipline, they may perceive this behavior as acceptable and adopt it in their own interactions.

Moreover, within the cultural and societal context of Abakpa, Enugu State, there are certain norms and beliefs that condone or even encourage the use of corporal punishment and other forms of sanctions as disciplinary measures. These cultural norms, transmitted through social interactions and community practices, can shape individuals' attitudes and behaviors towards child rearing. Thus, children growing up in such environments are likely going to experience change through social learning.

In addressing the prevalence of child abuse in Abakpa, Enugu State, interventions based on the principles of SLT can be effective. By promoting positive parenting techniques and providing caregivers with resources and support networks, communities can help break the cycle of abuse. Moreover, raising awareness about the detrimental effects of child abuse and challenging cultural norms that condone violence are essential steps in creating a protective environment for children.

Research Hypotheses

Individuals with higher education are more likely to report cases of child abuse than those with lower education

There are significant relationships between notable implications of child abuse in Abakpa community and the ratings of their health experiences.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The study used cross-sectional design, adopted a quantitative research method to collect data from the respondents on the prevalence effect of child abuse on child's health in Abakpa community.

Study Area: The study area is Abakpa community. Abakpa is a large town located in the neighborhood of Enugu city, central Nigeria, located about 8 kilometers west of Akanu Ibiam International Airport and 7 kilometers north of Enugu city center. It is a commercial small settlement near Highway 343, with a few large commercial markets and farmer's shops. The number of residents has been recently increasing since some small industrial companies started operating in the town, so new residents looking for new career opportunities came to and settled in Abakpa. There are also several churches, markets, and stores in the town.

Study Population: According to the National Population Census (2006), Abakpa community has a population of two hundred and ten thousand, six hundred and thirty-three (210,633) people. This number represents the general population of the study, thus from this population, the study would focus on both males and females with both formal or no formal education, people from all occupations and marital status, parents, teachers and teens within the age of fourteen (14) to sixty five (65) who reside in Abakpa town. According to the official website of the Enugu State Government, there are 109 resident streets in Akpaba town Some of these include; Umuezebi Street, Umuagu Street, Umunnachi Street, Umuoji Crescent, Umuezegbe Street, Umuowa Lane, Ogui Road, Amaigbo Road, Nkpor Street, Ukwuorji Street, Umunneochi Crescent, Iyiowa Street, Ebeano Avenue, Ezere Street, Umumba Road, Umuokoro Street, Obodo-Ukwu Crescent, Ugwuaji Street, Umueze Street, Umuezukwe Street, Achara Street, Umuida Road, Umuoye Street, Obinagu Street, Umuene Street, Umunachi Road, Umueze Street, Umudim Street, Umuode Street, Umuoyere Street, Umuoboli Street, Umuorji Street, Umuduru

Street, Umuhu Street, Umuakwe Street, Umuakwu Crescent (www.enugustate.gov.ng).

Sample Size: Sample size of this study was two hundred (200) people consisting of children and adults from the range of 14 to 65 years. It was determined using Taro Yamani (1967) formula at 0.007 error limit. The sample was selected from the target population.

The Yamani (1967) was applied thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)}$$

Where; n = sample size

N= target population of study

e= error limit (0.05) or 0.0083

I= constant

Applying the above formula we have;

$$n = 210,633 \div 1 + 210,633 (0.005) = 1,053.165$$

$$210,633 \div 1,053.165 = 200$$

As a result the sample size for the study was 200 respondents.

Sampling Procedure: Multi stage sampling technique was adopted for the study which includes systematic random sampling, purposive sampling and availability sampling. Through systematic sampling 18 streets were selected out of the listed streets in Abakpa. They include; Umuezebi Street, Umannachi Street, Umuezegbe Street, Ogui Road, Nkpor Street, Umunneochi Crescent, Ebeano Avenue, Umumba Road, Obodo-Ukwu Crescent, Umuezukwe Street, Umuida Road, Umuene Street, Umueze Street, Umuode Street, Umuoboli Street, Umuduru Street, Umuhu Street, Umuakwu Crescent. Then using purposive sampling technique, 9 streets were selected depending on their closeness to each other; Akubueze Street, Nkpor street, Umuode street, Umuhu street Umuakwu Street, Umuoboli Street, Umuduru Street, Umuhu Street, and Mabia Street. Through availability sampling technique, questionnaires were shared to respondents from the selected streets.

Instrument for Data Collection: Questionnaire was used as the major instrument for data collection which comprises demographic characteristics of the respondents and the main research issues. The questionnaire was validated by three professionals and measured using likert scale of 1-4 with 1 not available, 2- rarely 3-moderately, 4- available. It was both self administered and others administered while In-depth interview served as a complementary data.

Methods of Data Analysis: The study applied a quantitative method of data analysis. The data collected from the field was computer-processed and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 20). Descriptive statistics such as percentages and frequency tables were used to present the responses from the items in the questionnaire. Chi-square (χ^2) was used to show the relationship that exists between the dependent and independent variables in order to determine the prevalence effects of child abuse on child's health implications in Abakpa community Enugu State, Nigeria as well as test the study hypotheses. Ethically, to give credence to this present study, the respondents were informed on the objectives of the study and they agreed to participate in this research by filling out consent forms. Also, issue of confidentiality was made known to them and any information that could lead to identifying respondents must be avoided.

Results

Table1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Age		
14-18 years	68	34.0
19-23 years	60	30.0
24-28years	25	12.5
29-33 years	20	10.0
34-38 years	12	6.0
39- 43years	10	5.0
44 – 65 years	5	2.5
Total	200	100
Occupation		
Students	128	64.0
Trader	37	18.5
Civil servant	23	11.5
Sales girls/Fuel pump attendants	12	6.0
Total	200	100

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Religious Affiliation		
Christianity	162	81.0
Muslim	9	4.5
African Traditional Religion	29	14.5
Total	200	100
Sex		
Female	112	56.0
Male	88	44.0
Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results from table 1 shows that out of seven categories of the age brackets, majority (34.0%) respondents were aged 14-18 years, (30.0%) respondents were 19-23 years, (12.5%) respondents were aged 24-28 years, (10%) 20 were aged 29-33 years while (6%) were aged 34-38 years ,(5%) aged 39- 43years and lastly, (2.5%) aged 44 years and above. On occupation, it shows that 64% of the respondents were students single, 18.5% of the respondents were traders, 11.5% of the respondents were civil servants and 6% of the respondents were sales girls and fuel pump attendants. The religious affiliation of the respondents indicates that (81%) respondents were Christians, (4.5%) respondents were Muslims, and (14.5%) respondents were practitioners of African Traditional Religion. The result may not be surprising since the study was carried out in Abapka community who are predominantly Christians. Lastly on sex of the respondents, out of a total of 200 respondents used for the study (44.0%) were male while (56.0%) were female. The sex distribution reflected females being more than males.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by level of education

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percent
Primary education	86	43.0
Secondary education	34	17.0
Tertiary education	3	1.5
No formal education	77	38.5
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 2 shows the educational status of the respondents. The results revealed that 43% only had primary school experience, 17% respondents had secondary school experience, 1.5 respondents were university students and 38.5% respondents had no formal education

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by level of income

Income	Frequency	Percent
Below 10,000	58	29.0
11000-20000	30	15.0
21000-30000	21	10.5
31000-40000	34	17.0
41000 and above	29	14.5
None	28	14.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 3 shows the income level of the respondents. The results revealed that (29%) respondents earn Below 10,000 monthly, (15%) respondents earn 11000-20000 monthly, (10.5%) of the respondents earn 21,000-30000 monthly, (17%) respondents earn 31000-40000 monthly, (14.5%) respondents earn 41000 and above. However, (14%) respondents earn nothing because they are just students.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents on if they have been Abused

If the respondents Abuse	Frequency	Percent
Yes	188	94.0
No	12	6.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 4 describes the knowledge level of the respondents on child abuse. The table shows that 94% have heard or are aware of child abuse while 6% of the respondents are not aware of it.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents on major causes of Child abuse in Abakpa

Causes of child abuse	Frequency	Percent
Poverty	141	70.5
Family instability	27	13.5
Illiteracy	31	15.5
Others	1	.5
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results from table 5 shows that 70.5% respondents reported poverty to be the major cause of child abuse in Abakpa, 13.5% respondents reported family instability to be the major cause of child abuse in Abakpa while 15.5% respondents were of the view that illiteracy is the major cause of child abuse in Abakpa. One respondent however opined that bad government was the major cause of child abuse in Abakpa.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents on the most prevalent form of Child abuse they have experienced

Most prevalent forms of child abuse they have experienced	Frequency	Percent
Physical child abuse	44	22.0
Sexual child abuse	65	32.5
Emotional abuse	58	29.0
Maid maltreatment	33	16.5
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results from table 6 shows that 22.0% of the respondents reported physical child abuse as the most occurring form of child abuse in Abakpa community, 32.5% reported sexual child abuse to be the most occurring form of child abuse in Abakpa, emotional abuse (29.0%), and lastly 16.5% noted it was maid maltreatment.

. Table 7: Distribution of respondents on if there are effects of abuses on the children health

If the respondents have experience the effect of child abuse on their health	Frequency	Percent
Yes	121	60.5
No	79	39.5
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results from Table 7 indicate that 60.5% (121) of respondents said yes, they have experience the effect of child abuse on their health while 39.5% (79) have not.

Table 8: Distribution of Respondents on the most notable effect of child abuse in Abakpa

Most notable effect of child abuse in Abakpa	Frequency	Percent
Low self esteem	81	40.5
Depression and anxiety	71	35.5

Bruises and injuries	48	24.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Results from table above table showed that 45% respondents were of the view that low self-esteem is the most occurring effect of child abuse in Abakpa, 38% respondents were of the view that depression and anxiety is the most occurring effect of child abuse in Abakpa while 17% respondents reported that bruises and injuries is the most occurring effect of child abuse in Abakpa.

Table 9: Distribution of Respondents on the ratings of experiences gotten from the respondents on child abuse

Rating of experiences from respondents	Frequency	Percent
Very high	82	41.0
High	53	26.5
Low	44	22.0
Very low	21	10.5
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2026

Results from table 9 shows that 41% respondents have received a very high abuse in rating while 26.5% rated high, 22% rated low and 10.5%, very low. Majority of the respondents 41% have experienced highest child abuse.

Table 10: Distribution of Respondents on whether children from poorly educated family background are more likely to experience child abuse in Abakpa

Family educational level	Frequency	Percent
Yes	143	71.5
No	37	18.5
I don't know	20	10.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2026

Results from table 10 shows that 71.5% respondents agreed children from poorly educated family background are more likely to experience child abuse in Abakpa while 18.5% respondents disagreed that children from poorly educated family background are more likely to experience child abuse in Abakpa. Another set of respondents 10% noted that they do not know whether children from poorly educated family background are more likely to experience child abuse in Abakpa.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis one

H_i: Individuals with lower educational qualification experiences child abuse more than those with higher educational qualification in Abakpa community.

H_o: Individuals with lower educational qualification experiences child abuse less than those with higher educational qualification in Abakpa community.

Test statistic: The Chi square (x^2) statistic was employed in testing this hypothesis.

Significance Level: A significance level of 0.05 was used in testing this hypothesis.

Table 11: Cross tabulation of respondents who have been abuse before and whether family educational level made children liable to abuse

	Whether family educational level made children liability to abuse		Total
	Yes	No	
Have you been abused before?			
Yes	169 (89.9%)	19 (10.1%)	188 (100.0%)
No	11 (91.7%)	1 (8.3%)	12 (100.0%)
Total	180 (90.0%)	20 (10.0%)	200(100.0%)

Fieldwork survey, 2026 Df 1 p 0.039

The table above is cross-tabulation of the respondents who has been abused before in Abakpa community and whether family educational level made children liable to abuse. It shows that 89.9% of the respondents noted that family individual’s level of education can affect a student’s liability to child abuse while 10.1% of the respondents noted that individual level of education cannot influence an individual liability to child abuse. The results from the chi square analysis shows that the p

value (0.039) is less than the alpha value (0.05), therefore we accept the substantive hypothesis which states that individual in low level of education are more likely to experience abuse than those with higher education and reject the null hypothesis which states that Individuals with higher education are less likely to experience child abuse than those with lower education in Abakpa.

Hypothesis two

Substantive hypothesis: There are significant relationships between most prevalent forms of child abuse and effect on children’s health in Abakpa community.

Null hypothesis: There are no significant relationships between most prevalent forms of child abuse and effect on children’s health in Abakpa community.

Test statistic: The Chi square (χ^2) statistic was employed in testing this hypothesis.

Significance Level: A significance level of 0.05 was used in testing this hypothesis.

Table 12: Cross tabulation of most prevalent forms of child abuse and if family income status affects children liability to child abuse.

Most prevalent forms of child abuse	If family income status affects children liability to child abuse		Total
	Yes	No	
Physical child abuse	44 (22.0%)	8 (4.0%)	52 (26.0%)
Sexual child abuse	115 (58.5%)	18 (9%)	136 (52.0%)
Emotional abuse	10 (5%)	6 (4%)	16 (8%)
Total	161(80.5%)	39 (14.5%)	200(100.0%)

Field survey, 2026 Df 1 p 0.013

The result from the chi square test shows that the p value (0.013) is less than the alpha value (0.05) thus the null hypothesis which stated that there are no significant relationships between most prevalent forms of child abuse and effect on children’s health was rejected while the substantive hypothesis which states that there are significant relationships between most prevalent forms of child abuse and effect on

children’s health in Abakpa community was accepted. Therefore, we conclude that individuals who have experienced most prevalent forms of child abuse are more likely to experience different health challenges than those who have not in Abakpa community.

Hypothesis three

Substantive hypothesis: There are significant relationships between notable implications of child abuse in Abakpa community and the ratings of their health experiences.

Null hypothesis: There are no significant relationship between notable implications of child abuse in Abakpa community and the rating of their health experiences.

Test statistic: The Chi square (χ^2) statistic was employed in testing this hypothesis.

Significance Level: A significance level of 0.05 was used in testing this hypothesis.

Table 13: Cross tabulation of most notable implication of child abuse in Abakpa community and ratings of their health experiences.

Most notable implication of child abuse in Abakpa community	Ratings on their health experiences	Total	
Low self esteem	81(81.0%)	19(19.0%)	100(100%)
Depression and anxiety	71(71.0%)	29(29.0%)	100(100%)
Total	152(76.0%)	48(24%)	200(100%)

Field survey, 2026 Df 1 p 0.001

The result from the chi square test shows that the p value (0.001) is less than the alpha value (0.05) thus the null hypothesis which stated that there are no notable implication of child abuse in Abakpa community based on the rating on their health experiences was rejected while the substantive hypothesis which states that there are notable implication of child abuse in Abakpa community based on the rating of their health experiences was accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the notable implications of child abuse in Abakpa community and the rating on their health experiences. The statistical analysis using chi-square confirmed a significant relationship between notable implications of child abuse in Abakpa community based on the rating on their health experiences, supporting the research hypothesis.

DISCUSSION

Child abuse is a social problem and as such sociologists and other social scientists should try to gain a better understanding about the problem and ways of addressing its recurrence in the society. Thus the study tries to ascertain the prevalence effect of child abuse on children's health in Abakpa community Enugu state Nigeria. The first finding from the study tries to ascertain if the respondents have experienced abuse in any form. Results show that 94% have experienced child abuse while only 6% of the respondents have not. This is in line with the findings of Brown (2020) who noted that parental stress can significantly contribute to child abuse, creating a challenging environment for both parents and children. High levels of stress may compromise a parent's ability to cope effectively, leading to frustration, anger, and decreased impulse control. This finding was supported by the data from the in-depth interview. Four out of the six parents interviewed responded that they are quite aware that child abuse has health implications on children. One of the parents said, "Child abuse is more pronounced among those children who live with their step mothers and those who live with other parents serving as house helps." This was confirmed by the nannies who stated that most times their madam will not be interested if you are sick or not, her concern is for you to do all you are expected to do. Supporting this qualitative data, Nelson et al., (2022) noted that one long-term study found that up to 80% of abused people had at least one psychiatric disorder at age 21, with problems including depression, anxiety, eating disorders, and suicide attempts.

Secondly, findings from the major causes of child abuse indicated that 70.5% was poverty, 13.5% indicated family instability, 15.5% said it was illiteracy and finally 0.5% said child maltreatment. Fayaz, (2019) noted that child maltreatment always occurs when any of these areas of a child's emotional and social growth are neglected or not given adequate attention.

Also results from the most prevalent forms of child abuses the respondents have experienced showed that 22.0% said physical abuse, 32.5% indicated sexual abuse, 29.0% indicated emotional abuse and 16.5% said child maltreatment. Brown (2020), reported that children from disadvantaged backgrounds are particularly susceptible to exploitation and mistreatment, as they often lack the protection and advocacy necessary to safeguard their rights. Also Zhang (2022), found out that low socio-economic status or poverty are the major cause of child abuse. In support of the above, according to Okechukwu & Nwafor (2019), the high prevalence of poverty and unemployment in Nigeria places immense pressure on parents to provide for their families, leading to heightened stress levels and for them additionally, factors such as marital conflicts, substance abuse, and limited access to social support further compound parental stress and increase the risk of child abuse.

Findings on if there are effect of child abuse on the respondents' health, 60.5% said Yes while 39.5% said No. This result supported the second hypothesis which stated that there are significant relationships between most prevalent forms of child abuse and effect on children's health in Abakpa community. Also Bamiwuye et al.,(2017) indicated that in a country where poverty rates remain high and economic opportunities are limited, families often struggle to meet their basic needs, leading to increased stress and tension within households and parents facing economic hardship may be more prone to resorting to abusive behaviors as a means of exerting control or venting frustration. Zickler (2022) also opined that in addition to possible immediate adverse physical effects, household dysfunction and childhood maltreatment are strongly associated with many chronic physical and psychological effects, including subsequent ill-health in childhood, adolescence and adulthood, with higher rates of chronic conditions, high-risk health behaviors and shortened lifespan.

The study also investigated family's educational level and child abuse, the study found out that majority of the respondents , 71.5% .This is in line with hypothesis one which states that individuals with lower education qualifications are more likely to experience child abuse than those with higher education qualification in Abakpa. A study conducted in China by Guochen et al. (2023), also noted that 72.6% of the children abused came from poorly educated family background while the rest 27.4 came from well-educated family background.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the prevalence effect of child abuse on child' health in Abakpa is a deeply concerning issue that demands urgent attention and concerted action from all stakeholders. Family socioeconomic status (educational and income level) are among the most important risk factors for child abuse. Children who live with parents of low socioeconomic status are at high risk for abuse. The distressing statistics reveal not only the scale of the problem but also its profound effect on the health and well-being of the community's children. From physical injuries to psychological trauma, sexual abuse which can result to contamination of diseases such as HIV, Aids etc, the health implications of child abuse are far-reaching and long-lasting, affecting individuals and society as a whole.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Efforts should be made by the state and federal government as well as nongovernmental organizations to improve the welfare and cost of living of families living in Slum areas like Abakpa; this would help in reducing the

problem in the area since socio-economic status is a dominant factor of child abuse.

2. Efforts should also be made by the university governing bodies to set up programs, workshops and synopsis that would enlighten parents on the causes and dangers of child abuse especially as it pertains to their health.
3. The government of Enugu State should invest in the establishment and enhancement of child protection services and support systems across the state especially in slum areas like Abakpa. This includes expanding access to counseling, rehabilitation, and mental health services for both victims and perpetrators. Additionally, provide training for social workers, healthcare professionals, and educators to identify proprietors of abuse, provide appropriate intervention, and offer ongoing support to affected children and families.
4. To effectively address the problem of child abuse in Abakpa, it is imperative to implement comprehensive strategies that prioritize prevention, protection, and support. This includes strengthening child protection laws, enhancing law enforcement efforts, raising awareness, and providing accessible and culturally sensitive support services for victims and their families.
5. Furthermore, addressing the root causes of child abuse, such as poverty, social inequality, and lack of education, is essential for sustainable change. By working together, government agencies, community organizations, healthcare professionals, educators, and individuals can create a safer and healthier environment where every child in Abakpa can thrive free from the scourge of abuse.

REFERENCE

- Adekola, M.O, Oyeniyi, J.A & Gbenga-Epebinu, M.A (2022). Knowledge and attitude towards child abuse among married couples in Akure South Local government area, Akure, Ondo-State. *International Journal of Health and Psychology Research* 10(1), 1-17. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijhpr.13/vol10no1pp.1-17>
- Ahmad, S. & Zaitun B. (2020). Child Abuse and Security Challenges in Nigeria. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD)* Volume 4 Issue 2, February 2020 Available Online: www.ijtsrd.com e-ISSN: 2456 – 646483

- Bamiwuye, S., Odimegwu, C., & Spiff, O. (2017). Socioeconomic Factors Influencing Child Abuse and Neglect in Nigeria: A Study of Street Children and Child Labourers in Lagos State. *African Population Studies*, 28(3), 1318-1330
- Brown, D. (2020). "(Mis) representations of the long-term effects of childhood sexual abuse in the courts". *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*. 9 (3–4): 79–107. doi:10.1300/J070v09n03_05. PMID 17521992. S2CID 20874393.
- Browne, A. & Finkelhor, D. (2019). "Impact of child sexual abuse: a review of the research". *Psychological Bulletin*. 99 (1): 66–77. doi:10.1037/0033-2909.99.1.66. hdl:10983/681. PMID 3704036
- Bulik, C.M & Prescott C.A. (2021). "Features of childhood sexual abuse and the development of psychiatric and substance use disorders". *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 179 (5): 444–9. doi:10.1192/bjp.179.5.444. PMID 11689403
- Diaz, A., Shankar, V., Nucci-Sack, A., Linares, L. Salandy, A. Strickler D.& Burk (2020). Effect of child abuse and neglect on risk behaviors in inner-city minority female adolescents and young adults
- Fayaz, I. (2019). Child Abuse: Effects and Preventive Measures. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*. 7(2): 871-884.
- Fergusson, D.M. & Mullen, P.E. (2019). Childhood abuse: An evidence based perspective. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications. ISBN 978-0-7619-1136-4.
- Gbenga-Epebinu M.A., Okafor N.A & Olofinbiyi R.O. (2020). Perception of Child abuse Among Couples in Ilokun Community in Ado Local Government Area, Ekiti state. *Euro Afro Studies International Journal*. 1(3), 1-13. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3735450
- Holguin G. & Hansen D. J. (2023). "The abused child": Potential mechanisms of adverse influences of such a label". *Aggression and Violent Behavior*. 8 (6): 645–670. doi:10.1016/S1359-1789(02)00101
- Lund T.J., Dearing E. & Zacharisson H.D. (2017). Is affluence a risk for adolescents in Norway? *J. Res. Adolesc.*;27:628643. doi: 10.1111/jora.12304.
- Nelson E.C., Heath A.C. & Madden P.A. (2022). "Association between self-reported childhood abuse and adverse psychosocial outcomes: results from a twin study". *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 59 (2): 139–145. doi:10.1001

- Obuzor A. & Gabriel-Job N. (2022). Street hawking among children: A form of child abuse often overlooked. *International Journal of Tropical Disease & Health*, 43(11), 38-44.
- Okechukwu C. & Nwafor C. E. (2019). Parental Stress and Child Abuse in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities, Arts, Medicine and Sciences*. 7(2), 64-71.
- Olubukola O., Olatosi P, Folakemi A. & Site, E. (2018). Experiences and Knowledge of Child Abuse and Neglect: A survey among group of resident doctors in Nigeria. *Nigeria Postgraduate Medical journal*. 25 (4), 225-233.
- Torsheim T., Nygren J.M., Rasmussen M. & Arnarsson A.M. (2018). Social inequalities in self-rated health: A comparative cross national study among 32,560 Nordic adolescents. *Scand. J. Public Health*;46:150156. doi: 10.1177/1403494817734733.
- Ugochukwu T. & Onoka A. (2018). The prevalence of child abuse sexual abuse, sexual assault and revictimization in Onitsha. Vol. 1. *Child Rights Acts*, CA: Praeger. pp. 203–216 doi: 10.1177/889349481773353637.
- UNICEF (2024). Sexual violence <https://www.unicef.org/press-releases/nearly-400-million-young-children-worldwide-regularly-experience-violent-discipline>
- UNICEF (2024). Sexual violence. <https://data.unicef.org/topic/child-protection/violence/sexual-violence/#status>
- United Nations Children’s Fund, *Child Marriage and the Law: Legislative Reform Initiative Paper Series* [http://www.unicef.org/policyanalysis/files/child_marriage_and_the_law\(1\)](http://www.unicef.org/policyanalysis/files/child_marriage_and_the_law(1)).
- Walsh K. DiLillo D. (2021). "Child sexual abuse and adolescent sexual assault and revictimization". In Paludi, Michael A. (ed.). *The psychology of teen violence and victimization*. Vol. 1. Santa Barbara, CA: Praeger. pp. 203–216. ISBN 978-0-313-39375-4.
- Widom C. S. (2019). The cycle of violence. *Science*, 244(4901), 160-166
- Yahaya I. Mohammed M., Gabriel V. & Oladipo (2016). The consequences of child abuse on self esteem: Anxiety and depression as aftermaths of a child abuse doi: 10.1007/s10964-007-9247-6.
- Zhang R., Xie R., Ding W., Wang X., Song S. & Li W. (2022). "Why is my world so dark? Effects of child physical and emotional abuse on child depression: The mediating role of self-compassion and negative automatic thoughts.

Zickler, P. (2022). "Childhood Sex Abuse Increases Risk for Drug Dependence in Adult Women". NIDA Notes. National Institute of Drug Abuse. 17 (1): 5. doi:10.1151/v17i1CSAIRDDAW